

Exams Timetable Scheduler Modelling

Abubakar Muhammad¹
Computer Science Department,
Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi,
(Nigeria)
fajeer4sure@gmail.com
+2348125476248

Abstract

Exams timetable is a challenging area in the academics, particularly where its design is done manually. The challenges emerge in the form of clashes of exams or invigilation, omissions of exams or invigilation. To avoid error of clashes many techniques, most are mathematical in nature, were employed and one of such is graph colouring. Unique colours were assigned to exams and invigilation and in each exam schedule no same colours are allowed to feature. This makes clashes impossible. This paper attempts to employ graph colouring technique to produce physical model of computerized examination scheduler that will tackle error of clashes. The case study is federal polytechnic, Bauchi and the paper and the research is sponsored by TETFUND. A physical model that can be implemented on Oracle database management system is produced in this paper.

Keywords: model, entity, logical model, physical model, conceptual model.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Graph Colouring

Damara *et al.*, 2014 explains what graph colouring is where he said, “**Graph colouring**” is a special case of graph labelling; it is an assignment of labels traditionally called "colours" to elements of a graph subject to certain constraints. In its simplest form, it is a way of colouring the vertices of a graph such that no two adjacent vertices share the same colour; this is also called a **vertex colouring**. Similarly, an **edge colouring** assigns a colour to each edge so that no two adjacent edges share the same colour, and a **face colouring** of a planar graph assigns a colour to each face or region so that no two faces that share a boundary have the same colour. Vertex colouring is the starting point of the subject, and other colouring problems can be transformed into a vertex version.”

Fig. 1 Vertex colouring with 3 colours [Source Damara et al, 2014]

One of the most common academic scheduling problems which can be perceived in any educational system is the exam time table generation. The presence of vast numbers of students and offered courses makes it difficult to schedule exams in a limited epoch of time. An appropriate schedule can be designed by utilizing different resources like subjects, teachers, students and classrooms in a way to evade conflicts by fulfilling special types of constraints. Graph colouring is one decent approach which can deal with timetable scheduling problem and can satisfy changing requirements (Kumar and Duarah, 2018). Problem constraint can be unary involving one variable, binary involving two and high order involving three or more variables. (Automatyki & Gorniczko, 2010).

Burke *et al* stated that, “The application of computers to timetabling problems has a long and varied history. Almost as soon as computers were first built there were attempts to use them to solve these problems. The first generation of computer timetabling programs in the early 1960’s was largely an attempt to reduce the associated administration work. Soon programs were presented with the aim of fitting classes and teachers to periods. In 1964 Broder and Cole both presented heuristic approaches to timetabling.”.

A graph G , is a non-empty finite set V of vertices (nodes) and a non-empty finite set E of edges (arcs) [4] [5] [11]. So, a graph G can be represented as an ordered of $(V(G), E(G))$ consisting of a non-empty set V of vertices or nodes, where $E \subseteq V \times V$. An undirected graph could be pictorially represented as Figure-1, where, $V = \{A, B, C\}$, and $E = \{(A, C), (B, C), (A, B)\}$. Here $e_1 = (A, C)$, $e_2 = (B, C)$ and $e_3 = (A, B)$ (Kumar and Duarah, 2018).

Fig. 2 an example of graph [Source: Kumar & Duarah, 2018]

Fig. 3 Vertex colouring satisfying constraints of graph colouring [Source: Kumar & Duarah, 2018]

Figure 3 shows four vertices satisfying the constraint of graph colouring that no neighbouring vertices should have the same colour. Neighbouring means the vertices have edge connecting them.

1.2 Data Modelling

Business analysis is a discipline that has been evolving for about 20 years. Its main purpose is to ensure that there is alignment between business needs and business change solutions. Many of these business change solutions involve the development of new – or the enhancement of existing – information technology (commonly abbreviated to IT) systems (Gordon, 2017).

Fig. 4 three levels of system [Source: Gordon, 2017]

The business analyst needs to think in terms of three levels of system: the business system itself; the subsystem that handles the information for the business (the information

system); and the sub-subsystem that provides the technology to support the information system (the IT system). This is shown diagrammatically in Figure 4 (Gordon, 2017).

The what model is a conceptual model, which is also known as a Computer-Independent Model (CIM). It represents the things that are of interest to the business about which information needs to be recorded, the specific information about these things that the business needs recorded, and any business relationships that exist between those things of interest. A model at this level can be considered as encapsulating the rules of the business, for example:

- a) y ‘people or organisations cannot be recorded as customers until they have placed an order’;
- b) y ‘customers can place many orders’; and
- c) y ‘customers must be allocated a customer number and we must record their name and address.

The system development team then develop a series of how data models that lead to the design of the system’s database. The first model the developers will produce will be a logical model (often known as a Logical Data Model (LDM) or a PlatformIndependent Model (PIM)) and the final model will be a model that represents the actual physical design of the database (known as a Physical Data Model (PDM) or a Platform-Specific Model (PSM)) (Gordon, 2017).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Federal polytechnic, Bauchi operates manual method of scheduling exams timetable for its numerous classes and having known that manual scheduling is naturally associated with several flaws which includes slow, clashes and omissions; computerization is conceived. The very first challenge is that of modelling the data effectively which will culminate in efficient model and which in turn will give database that can stand and will match the aspirations behind the entire project. Modelling of data is essential to the success of software design project and many defects are tackled at the level of modelling. This paper studies the modelling of data in the computerization process.

3. AIM & OBJECTIVES

The aim of this paper is to model the manual exams timetable scheduling system at federal polytechnic, Bauchi as the first step toward automating the system.

4. SCOPE OF STUDY

In modelling the manual exams scheduling system at federal polytechnic, Bauchi, baker notation is adopted and Oracle SQL developer data modeler is employed.

5. METHODOLOGY

The data modelling notation adopted in this paper is Baker notation because of its wider acceptance in modelling communities. The requirement analysis employs the use of:

- a) Record inspection and
- b) Interview

In order to collect business rules behind the manual system. The modelling tool employed in the research is Oracle SQL developer data modeler.

6. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The central exams timetable committee of federal polytechnic, Bauchi provided this research with extract of the exams timetable scheduling process done at the committee level manually. This document became the major source of deriving business rules for the system. Later interview was conducted to the secretary of the committee to further explains some of the issues raised by the document. From these two sources, the following potentials entities were conceived:

Fig. 5 Potential entities in Poly Exams App

Figure 5 shows the potential entities with no relationship created, except that to capture data changes. While figure 6 shows the logical model with relationships and attributes created.

Fig. 6 Logical model of Poly Exams

After normalization by creating intersecting entities, the logical model was refined to produce the one shown in figure 7:

Fig. 7 Normalized Logical Model of Poly Exams App

The finished logical model is forward engineered using Oracle SQL developer data modeler to produce physical model which is shown in figure 8.

Fig. 8 Physical model of Poly Exams App

After physical model is engineered, then DDL file is generated which is an SQL file compliant with Oracle proprietary standard. The DDL codes were modified to go with the SQL standard so that it can be used to create database using any database management system without hedges. The standard codes are shown below:

```
-- Generated by Oracle SQL Developer Data Modeler
19.2.0.182.1216
```

```
-- at:          2023-02-05 15:38:20 WAT
-- site:        Oracle Database 11g
-- type:        Oracle Database 11g
```

```
CREATE TABLE academic_calendars (
    exams_begin    DATE NOT NULL,
    ses            VARCHAR(25 ) NOT NULL,
    semester       ENUM("First","Second") NOT NULL,
    exams_end      DATE NOT NULL,
    holidays       DATE,
    timetables_id  INTEGER NOT NULL
);
```

```
CREATE UNIQUE INDEX academic_calendars__idx ON
    academic_calendars (
        timetables_id
    ASC );
```

```
ALTER TABLE academic_calendars ADD CONSTRAINT
academic_calendars_pk PRIMARY KEY ( exams_begin );
```

```
CREATE TABLE assign_courses (
    dad            DATE NOT NULL,
    examinable_coures_cod  VARCHAR(10 ) NOT NULL,
    programmes_id  INTEGER NOT NULL
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE assign_courses ADD CONSTRAINT assign_courses_pk
PRIMARY KEY ( examinable_coures_cod,
programmes_id );
```

```
CREATE TABLE committee_memberships (
    djd            DATE NOT NULL,
    committees_id  INTEGER NOT NULL
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE committee_memberships ADD CONSTRAINT
committee_memberships_pk PRIMARY KEY ( committees_id );
```

```
CREATE TABLE committees (
    id            INTEGER NOT NULL,
    first_name    VARCHAR(50 ) NOT NULL,
    last_name     VARCHAR(100 ) NOT NULL,
    phone         VARCHAR(11 ),
    email         TEXT NOT NULL,
```

```
        status          ENUM("Active","Inactive" ) NOT NULL,  
        types           ENUM("Chairman","Secretary","Representative")  
NOT NULL,  
        username       VARCHAR(12 ),  
        pwd            TEXT NOT NULL,  
        sqn            TEXT NOT NULL,  
        sar            TEXT NOT NULL  
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE committees ADD CONSTRAINT committees_pk PRIMARY  
KEY ( id );  
ALTER TABLE committees MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL  
AUTO_INCREMENT;
```

```
CREATE TABLE deans (  
        id              INTEGER NOT NULL,  
        names           TEXT,  
        schools_id      INTEGER NOT NULL  
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE deans ADD CONSTRAINT deans_pk PRIMARY KEY ( id );  
ALTER TABLE deans MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT;
```

```
CREATE TABLE departments (  
        id              INTEGER NOT NULL,  
        names           TEXT NOT NULL,  
        abr             VARCHAR(15 ),  
        email           TEXT NOT NULL,  
        phone           VARCHAR(11 ),  
        address         TEXT NOT NULL,  
        schools_id      INTEGER NOT NULL  
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE departments ADD CONSTRAINT departments_pk PRIMARY  
KEY ( id );  
ALTER TABLE departments MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL  
AUTO_INCREMENT;
```

```
CREATE TABLE examinable_coures (  
        cod             VARCHAR(10 ) NOT NULL,  
        ttl             TEXT NOT NULL,  
        unt             INTEGER NOT NULL,  
        departments_id  INTEGER  
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE examinable_coures ADD CONSTRAINT  
examinable_coures_pk PRIMARY KEY ( cod );
```

```
CREATE TABLE hods (  
    id                INTEGER,  
    names             TEXT,  
    departments_id    INTEGER NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE invigilation_schedules (  
    id                INTEGER NOT NULL,  
    chief_invigilator TEXT NOT NULL,  
    invigilator       TEXT NOT NULL  
);
```

```
ALTER TABLE invigilation_schedules ADD CONSTRAINT  
invigilation_schedules_pk PRIMARY KEY ( id );  
ALTER TABLE invigilation_schedules MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL  
AUTO_INCREMENT;
```

```
CREATE TABLE posting_histories (  
    dpd                DATE NOT NULL,  
    staff_stf_psn      VARCHAR(15 ) NOT NULL,  
    departments_id     INTEGER NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE UNIQUE INDEX posting_histories__idx ON  
posting_histories (  
    departments_id  
ASC );
```

```
ALTER TABLE posting_histories ADD CONSTRAINT  
posting_histories_pk PRIMARY KEY ( staff_stf_psn );
```

```
CREATE TABLE programmes (  
    id                INTEGER NOT NULL,  
    ses               VARCHAR(15 ) NOT NULL,  
    names             VARCHAR(100)  
-- ERROR: Datatype UNKNOWN is not allowed  
    NOT NULL,  
    abr               VARCHAR(15 ),  
    typ               ENUM("National Diploma","Higher National  
Diploma" ) NOT NULL,  
    class             TEXT NOT NULL,  
    sze               INTEGER NOT NULL,  
    stream            ENUM("A","B")  
-- ERROR: Datatype UNKNOWN is not allowed
```

```
        NOT NULL,
        departments_id    INTEGER,
        timetables_id     INTEGER NOT NULL
    );

CREATE UNIQUE INDEX programmes__idx ON
    programmes (
        timetables_id
    ASC );

ALTER TABLE programmes ADD CONSTRAINT programmes_pk PRIMARY
KEY ( id );
ALTER TABLE programmes MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL
AUTO_INCREMENT;

CREATE TABLE rep_histories (
    dnd          DATE NOT NULL,
    schools_id    INTEGER NOT NULL,
    committees_id INTEGER NOT NULL
);

CREATE UNIQUE INDEX rep_histories__idx ON
    rep_histories (
        committees_id
    ASC );

ALTER TABLE rep_histories ADD CONSTRAINT rep_histories_pk
PRIMARY KEY ( schools_id );

CREATE TABLE schools (
    id          INTEGER NOT NULL,
    names       TEXT NOT NULL,
    email       TEXT NOT NULL,
    phone       VARCHAR(15 ) NOT NULL,
    adresss     TEXT
);

ALTER TABLE schools ADD CONSTRAINT schools_pk PRIMARY KEY ( id
);
ALTER TABLE schools MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT;

CREATE TABLE staff (
    stf_psn          VARCHAR(15 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_first_name   VARCHAR(100 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_last_name    VARCHAR(100 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_ttl          VARCHAR(5 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_email        TEXT NOT NULL,
    stf_phone        VARCHAR(15 ),
```

```

    stf_stu          VARCHAR(25 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_cadre        VARCHAR(25 ) NOT NULL,
    stf_rnk          VARCHAR(50 ),
    stf_gl           INTEGER,
    stf_sex          VARCHAR(10 ) NOT NULL,
    invigilation_schedules_id  INTEGER NOT NULL,
    nac_gl           INTEGER,
    amc_rnk          VARCHAR(100 )
);

ALTER TABLE staff ADD CONSTRAINT staff_pk PRIMARY KEY (
stf_psn );

CREATE TABLE timetables (
    id               INTEGER NOT NULL,
    day              VARCHAR(100 ) NOT NULL,
    tme              VARCHAR(100 ) NOT NULL,
    cod              VARCHAR(10 ) NOT NULL,
    ttl              TEXT NOT NULL,
    invigilation_schedules_id  INTEGER NOT NULL
);

CREATE UNIQUE INDEX timetables__idx ON
    timetables (
        invigilation_schedules_id
    ASC );

ALTER TABLE timetables ADD CONSTRAINT timetables_pk PRIMARY
KEY ( id );
ALTER TABLE timetables MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL
AUTO_INCREMENT;

CREATE TABLE venue (
    id               INTEGER NOT NULL,
    names            VARCHAR(200 ) NOT NULL,
    abr              VARCHAR(25 ),
    capacity         INTEGER NOT NULL,
    stu              ENUM("Available","Unavailable" ) NOT NULL,
    typ              ENUM("Class","Hall","Workshop","Laboratory","Drawing
Room","Typing Pool" ) NOT NULL,
    address          TEXT,
    timetables_id   INTEGER
);

ALTER TABLE venue ADD CONSTRAINT venue_pk PRIMARY KEY ( id );
ALTER TABLE venue MODIFY id INTEGER NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT;
```

```
ALTER TABLE academic_calendars
  ADD CONSTRAINT acrs_ttes_fk FOREIGN KEY ( timetables_id )
    REFERENCES timetables ( id );

ALTER TABLE assign_courses
  ADD CONSTRAINT ace_eces_fk FOREIGN KEY (
  examinable_coures_cod )
    REFERENCES examinable_coures ( cod );

ALTER TABLE assign_courses
  ADD CONSTRAINT aces_pge_fk FOREIGN KEY ( programmes_id )
    REFERENCES programmes ( id );

ALTER TABLE committee_memberships
  ADD CONSTRAINT cmp_cmes_fk FOREIGN KEY ( committees_id )
    REFERENCES committees ( id );

ALTER TABLE deans
  ADD CONSTRAINT deans_schools_fk FOREIGN KEY ( schools_id )
    REFERENCES schools ( id );

ALTER TABLE departments
  ADD CONSTRAINT departments_schools_fk FOREIGN KEY (
  schools_id )
    REFERENCES schools ( id );

ALTER TABLE examinable_coures
  ADD CONSTRAINT ece_dpt_fk FOREIGN KEY ( departments_id )
    REFERENCES departments ( id );

ALTER TABLE hods
  ADD CONSTRAINT hods_departments_fk FOREIGN KEY (
  departments_id )
    REFERENCES departments ( id );

ALTER TABLE posting_histories
  ADD CONSTRAINT phy_dpt_fk FOREIGN KEY ( departments_id )
    REFERENCES departments ( id );

ALTER TABLE posting_histories
  ADD CONSTRAINT posting_histories_staff_fk FOREIGN KEY (
  staff_stf_psn )
    REFERENCES staff ( stf_psn );

ALTER TABLE programmes
  ADD CONSTRAINT programmes_departments_fk FOREIGN KEY (
  departments_id )
    REFERENCES departments ( id );
```

```
ALTER TABLE programmes
  ADD CONSTRAINT programmes_timetables_fk FOREIGN KEY (
timetables_id )
  REFERENCES timetables ( id );

ALTER TABLE rep_histories
  ADD CONSTRAINT rep_histories_committees_fk FOREIGN KEY (
committees_id )
  REFERENCES committees ( id );

ALTER TABLE rep_histories
  ADD CONSTRAINT rep_histories_schools_fk FOREIGN KEY (
schools_id )
  REFERENCES schools ( id );

ALTER TABLE staff
  ADD CONSTRAINT staff_ise_fk FOREIGN KEY (
invigilation_schedules_id )
  REFERENCES invigilation_schedules ( id );

ALTER TABLE timetables
  ADD CONSTRAINT timetables_ise_fk FOREIGN KEY (
invigilation_schedules_id )
  REFERENCES invigilation_schedules ( id );

ALTER TABLE venue
  ADD CONSTRAINT venue_timetables_fk FOREIGN KEY (
timetables_id )
  REFERENCES timetables ( id );

-- CREATE OR REPLACE TRIGGER fkntm_academic_calendars BEFORE
--   UPDATE OF timetables_id ON academic_calendars
--BEGIN
--
--END;
/
-- Oracle SQL Developer Data Modeler Summary Report:
--
-- CREATE TABLE          16
-- CREATE INDEX           5
-- ALTER TABLE          32
-- CREATE VIEW            0
-- ALTER VIEW            0
-- CREATE PACKAGE         0
-- CREATE PACKAGE BODY   0
-- CREATE PROCEDURE       0
-- CREATE FUNCTION       0
```

```
-- CREATE TRIGGER 1
-- ALTER TRIGGER 0
-- CREATE COLLECTION TYPE 0
-- CREATE STRUCTURED TYPE 0
-- CREATE STRUCTURED TYPE BODY 0
-- CREATE CLUSTER 0
-- CREATE CONTEXT 0
-- CREATE DATABASE 0
-- CREATE DIMENSION 0
-- CREATE DIRECTORY 0
-- CREATE DISK GROUP 0
-- CREATE ROLE 0
-- CREATE ROLLBACK SEGMENT 0
-- CREATE SEQUENCE 0
-- CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW 0
-- CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW LOG 0
-- CREATE SYNONYM 0
-- CREATE TABLESPACE 0
-- CREATE USER 0
--
-- DROP TABLESPACE 0
-- DROP DATABASE 0
--
-- REDACTION POLICY 0
--
-- ORDS DROP SCHEMA 0
-- ORDS ENABLE SCHEMA 0
-- ORDS ENABLE OBJECT 0
```

7. CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS & ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Using Oracle SQL developer data modeler, the business rules identified in federal polytechnic, Bauchi exams timetable scheduling was modelled into logical and physical model. Thereafter, DDL codes for creating database structure was generated. This will pave the way for the Poly Exams Application design, with the backend fully modeled.

It is recommended that the DDL codes can be used to create database structure for automation of exams timetable scheduling system.

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Author(s)

1

Abubakar Muhammad

He instructed Computer Science courses in Professor Iya Abubakar Community Resource Centre, Bauchi as Consultant Instructor and later as Permanent Instructor. He also instructed different Computer related courses in Institute of Computer & Management Studies, Bauchi and is a CEO of Gwani Software limited, an ICT Solutions Provider Company based in Bauchi town. He served as a facilitator with National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). He had his Bachelor of Technology Degree in Computer Science, Post Graduate Diploma and Masters Degree from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi and pursuing Ph.D. computer science at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. He is currently a staff of The Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi in Department of Computer Science. He is an Oracle Database certified associate. His research focus is applications of Artificial Intelligence & Expert System in Digital Economy.